

The Role of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in Youth Empowerment and Wealth Creation in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper emphasizes Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) as a panacea to youth unemployment. It maintains that TVET is a tool for empowering people, especially the youth, for sustainable livelihood and economic development. TVET serves as a vital instrument for producing skilled manpower for various sectors of the national economy, thereby creating employment opportunities and contributing to wealth generation. However, the goal of using TVET to create jobs and generate wealth has not fully achieved the objectives outlined in the Federal Government of Nigeria's National Policy on Education (NPE). As a result, the role of TVET in empowering youths and reducing unemployment, underemployment, and associated social vices remains largely unrealized. The paper reviews key challenges contributing to this gap and recommends, among others, that the government and TVET stakeholders collaborate to revitalize TVET at all levels. Furthermore, the government should urgently raise its education budget to meet international standards, and Nigerian youths should be continually supported with credit facilities to help them establish small businesses rather than rely on limited white-collar jobs.

Keywords: TVET, Youth Empowerment, Wealth Creation

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Introduction

One of the recommended strategies for diversifying the Nigerian economy is the adoption of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) to develop a skilled workforce and entrepreneurs who can become employers of labour. This, in turn, contributes to job creation and wealth generation, ultimately boosting the nation's economic growth. Many countries both developed and developing recognize the critical role TVET plays in equipping individuals with relevant skills and knowledge, thereby enabling them to effectively participate in social, economic, and technological innovation (Netherlands Organization for International Cooperation in Higher Education [NICHE], 2010). Ayonmike and Okeke (2015) assert that embracing TVET is a key indicator of progress in Nigeria's economic diversification agenda, as it remains a major driver of national growth and development. TVET has the potential to produce skilled manpower for various sectors of the economy, creating employment opportunities and contributing to national development through wealth generation. However, the practical outcomes of TVET in Nigeria have not aligned with the expectations outlined in the Federal Government's National Policy on Education (NPE). Some graduates of TVET programmes lack employable and occupational skills, while others with such skills remain unemployed. This reality poses a serious threat to the goal of job creation and wealth generation through TVET. The persistent complaints from federal agencies and NGOs about the lack of job opportunities have discouraged many graduates, leaving them disillusioned and less motivated to seek employment. Consequently, Nigeria faces ongoing challenges related to youth unemployment, a mismatch between skills and labour market needs, and the increasing vulnerability of unemployed youths to poverty and recruitment into violent extremism. These evolving global socio-economic and political challenges place significant demands on educational systems. As such, educational administrators and planners must take active steps to address the consequences of youth unemployment. While the United Nations defines youth as individuals aged 15–24 years (Awogbenle & Iwuamadi, 2010), in Nigeria, the age range for youth is broader, extending from 12 to 30 years (International Labour Organization [ILO], 2005).

In Nigeria, youth unemployment remains one of the most critical socio-economic and political challenges, posing threats to national stability, security, and economic growth, and impeding sustainable development. The problem has persisted since the country's economic downturn in the late 1970s. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Nigeria's unemployment rate was 23.9% in 2011, up from 21.1% in 2010 and 19.7% in 2009. The rate has continued to rise, with youth unemployment exceeding 50% and growing at an estimated 11% annually. This trend reflects widespread poverty and economic hardship, particularly among the youth, who make up over 50% of Nigeria's population (Nwodoh, 2020). Musari (2009) notes that over 4.5 million Nigerian youths enter the labour market annually, often without realistic prospects for employment. Despite being a predominantly youthful society, Nigeria struggles to address youth unemployment effectively due to limited access to empowerment opportunities that foster self-employment and self-determination. The development of young people is essential to national economic resilience and productivity. To enhance their standard of living and increase their

competitiveness in the labour market, Nigerian youth require access to functional and skills-based education. Such education must equip them with self-reliant capabilities that align with labour market demands and enable entrepreneurial engagement.

However, the limited availability of quality education and empowerment programmes has left many Nigerian youths trapped in a cycle of poverty, undermining their future prospects and confidence. The increasing rate of unemployment and the declining socioeconomic status of graduates have contributed to a waning public trust in formal education. Addressing this challenge requires a national commitment to youth empowerment through accessible, practical, and quality education that supports self-reliance and sustainable livelihoods. In Nigeria, the National Policy on Youth Development (2001) defines a youth as any citizen between the ages of 18 and 35 years. Youths represent a nation's greatest asset and a beacon of hope for the future. According to the policy, the energy, creativity, character, and orientation of young people shape the development and security of a nation. Their productive skills and talents drive socio-economic progress, enabling a country to achieve significant economic and socio-political milestones. Youths occupy a prominent place in society, not only as future leaders but also as the largest demographic group in Nigeria. The National Bureau of Statistics (2010) reports that unemployment is one of the most serious economic challenges individuals face. A person is considered unemployed if they are willing and able to work but cannot find suitable employment.

Unemployment may not necessarily arise out of no vacancies in the economy as a whole, but essentially the unemployed may not possess the right skills for the available employment. Under employment occurs when the productive capacity of the employed labour is not fully utilized. On the other hand, self-employment involves economic activities by people who seize business opportunities and are able to take advantage of them, either alone or along with others. Empowerment refers to the ability of an individual to make choices regarding his or her life. It enhances an individual's or group's capacity to make choices and transform those choices into desired actions and outcome. If a person or group is empowered, they possess the capacity to make effective choices; that is, to translate their choices into desired actions and outcomes. Youth empowerment is an attitudinal, structural, and cultural process whereby young people gain the ability, authority, and agency to make decisions and implement change in their own lives and the lives of other people, including youths and adults. Thus, youth empowerment is a process of building an individual in the aspects of skill, economic and financial, social, moral and psychological development with the aim of making the individual self-reliant to him/herself and the society at large.

In order to achieve sustainable youth empowerment and national development in Nigeria, there must be adequate investment in skill-based training. The transformation of African economies into global competitive economies with abundant opportunities for decent work for the young population which constitutes a large portion of the continent's population has been hinged on investment of relevant skills and knowledge (World Economic Forum, 2015). Skill-based education is thus recognized as the main vehicle for promoting and improving the status of youths. There is an urgent need to reposition education to effectively equip the youths with right skills of

empowerment to add value to the society. Education is signatory to major conventions protecting the rights of youths and also equipping the youths to be self-reliant provision of functional and qualitative education remains the best empowerment any government can give its citizens. To achieve sustainable youth empowerment and national development, there must be adequate investment in skill-based training.

This paper therefore advocates for Technical Vocational, Education and Training (TVET) as an effective educational tool for youth empowerment, economic growth and national transformation. It examines TVET in Nigeria, challenges to job creation and wealth generation, stakeholder's role in making TVET work to achieve the desired objectives of creating jobs and generate wealth in order to improve the lives of her citizens and the national economy.

Concept of Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET)

Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) is in all probability as old as humanity (Maclean & Wilson, 2009). TVET has been described by various scholars, academicians, organizations, and governments, among others, as any activity related to skills acquisition and the production of a skilled workforce to improve the economy and livelihood. TVET, sometimes also known as Vocational Education and Training (VET) or Career and Technical Education (CTE), can be regarded as a means of preparing for occupational fields and effective participation in the world of work. It also implies lifelong learning and preparation for responsible citizenship. In its broadest definition, TVET includes technical education, vocational education, vocational training, on-the-job training, or apprenticeship training, delivered in a formal and non-formal way (NICHE, 2010). According to Aftab and Mohd (2012), vocational education plays a significant role in providing the skilled workforce required for the development of any country. As well, Ayonmike and Okeke (2015), citing Inyang (2012), posited that TVET provides one of the most potent means for the development of skilled manpower as required by various sectors in the country's economy. Nowadays, TVET is regarded as an instrument in creating new employment opportunities and income-generating activities in the formal and informal sectors of the economy, the need for which has become more acute due to financial crisis. TVET can play an important role in economic development and poverty reduction if due attention is given to customizing or targeting education and training provision to local needs (NICHE, 2010).

Similarly, Abdullahi (2011) opined that TVET is an essential part of development for any nation to grow economically. In addition, TVET brings about technological advancement and aims to fit new manpower for employment and provide continuing training for those already qualified, so that they can keep pace with the modern and emerging work environment. As well, TVET is designed to develop skills that can be used in specific occupations or jobs (Olaitan, 1998 in Magida, Saba, & Namkere, 2013).

Currently, UNESCO estimates that some 80% of occupations are based on the application of technical and vocational skills to the world of work (Maclean & Wilson, 2009, citing UNESCO-UNEVOC & UNESCO-UIS, 2006). Various types of TVET exist in different countries and these

TVET programmes are established to solve immediate and future needs regarding technological development. Technical Vocational education and training (TVET) is that part of tertiary education and training which provides accredited training in job related and technical skills. VTE is education that prepares the trainee for jobs or careers at various levels trade or craft. VTE focuses on practical applications of skills learned and education in vocational schools is hands-on training. Vocational training is therefore a link between education and the working world. VTE Qualifications are offered at registered and accredited Federal Education Technical Colleges, private institutions and workplaces. Institutes of Technology also offer VTE at a post-secondary level. It is important to note that the content for VTE programmes and qualifications is informed by relevant industries and not government or training institutions, making the programmes relevant to industry needs and fit-for-purpose. It covers a large number of careers and industries like trades and office work, retail, hospitality and technology. Skills are vital for poverty reduction, economic recovery and sustainable development. As a consequence, policy attention to Technical Vocational education and training (TVET) is increasing worldwide.

TVET comprises formal, non-formal and informal learning for the world of work. Young people, women and men learn knowledge and skills from basic to advanced levels across a wide range of institutional and work settings and in diverse socio-economic contexts. UNESCO leads the global debate by advocating for the rethinking of TVET to enhance its role in developing more equitable and sustainable societies. Vocational Education Technical (VET) can be considered as an engine for economic growth as it is one of the most effective human resource development strategies.

In an emerging economy such as Nigeria, once the biggest economy in Africa (Ololade, 2015), the role of Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) as a central hub for propelling the overall economic emancipation of the society through mass skill delivery cannot be overemphasized. It is, therefore, a statement of fact that TVET has no rival in skill development. While other aspects of education may lay claim to skill-centeredness, TVET is more skill-delivery sensitive than all other sectors. Hence, Uwaifo (2009), in Ojo, Adebayo, Ogumbodede, Bakare, Adeyemo, and Edoka (2017), stated that Technical Education, and by implication, TVET, has direct impact on the development of any country. The Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2000), in agreement, posited that TVET is a major part of technology education, which encompasses public knowledge, attitudes, and skills for making, doing, and using things in specifiable and reproducible ways. In the same vein, Okwori (2010) asserted that TVET is the only way to enhance productivity, wealth creation, and poverty alleviation for individuals and society in general.

From the foregoing, therefore, TVET can be said to be one of the most effective means of empowering youths not only to overcome poverty but also to reduce the incidence of social vices due to joblessness, and to promote a culture of peace, freedom, and democracy. Ironically, it is expected that graduates of TVET institutions, with their certificates and supposed skills, should be exempted from the teeming number of unemployed youths roaming the streets in search of government jobs or perpetrating various forms of social vices. To corroborate this, Abdulkerim (2014), citing Lemchi and Anyakoha (2002), stated that vocational education traditionally prepares

individuals for the world of work, yet many of the graduates still roam about in search of jobs. These youths are expected to venture into private businesses which would keep them out of the streets and out of trouble. On the contrary, however, the achievement of this objective through TVET development has continued to be elusive, as TVET institutions have continuously failed to produce self-reliant graduates. As such, the engagement of youths in all manners of nefarious activities has become the order of the day across Nigeria.

In light of the above, and in recognition of the importance of TVET for the overall emancipation of individuals and society in general, successive governments in Nigeria have strategically placed TVET within national educational policies since independence, as an instrument for mass skill delivery and youth empowerment. The climax of this commitment was the establishment of a master plan for Technical and Vocational Education (TVE) development in Nigeria in the 21st Century (FME, 2000). This initiative led to the proliferation of technical colleges, polytechnics, monotechnics, and universities across the country.

Goals of TVET

The goals of TVET were derived from the philosophy of the programme and society. However, around the world, the most commonly articulated goals of TVET are listed below:

1. To promote sustainable development, save the environment and improve the quality of living.
2. To reduce mass movement of school learners from rural to urban areas,
3. To facilitate economic development by transmitting to local citizens certain values, knowledge and attitudes that are necessary to perform certain skills in the modern sector of the economy.
4. To provide young people with the skills needed for employment in a wide range of job categories including self-employment and wage employment.
5. To promote a work ethic and sensitize learners to the importance of practical work skills and dignity of manual labour.
6. To alleviate unemployment as well as poverty
7. To provide an alternative route to higher academic education for early secondary school learners.

Specifically, the objectives of TVET in school system in Nigeria as listed in the National Policy of Education (2013) are:

- i. To provide trained manpower in applied science, technology, commerce particularly at sub-professional grades.
- ii. To provide technical skills necessary for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development.
- iii. To give an introduction to professional studies in engineering and other technologies.
- iv. To give training and improving the necessary skills leading to production of craftsmen, technical and other skilled personnel who will be enterprising and self reliant.

- v. To enable young men and women to have intelligent understanding of the increasing complexity of technology.

A critical examination of the objectives suggests that it was essentially a form of human resource development education. It was specifically designed to:

- i. Alleviate unemployment;
- ii. Re-orientate the attitudes of individuals- especially the youth-toward rural communities in order to curb urban migration; and
- iii. Transfer employment relevant skills

Youth Empowerment

Education is arguably the most powerful tool for empowering youth with knowledge, practical skills, and self-confidence (Nwodoh, 2021). The progress of any highly developed nation can largely be attributed to the quality and reach of its educational system. Education serves as a weapon for the advancement of the underprivileged, the marginalized, the uninformed, and the oppressed in society. Youth empowerment through education acts as a catalyst for sustainable economic growth and national development. The concept of youth empowerment becomes especially critical when addressing persistent societal challenges such as youth unemployment, poverty, poor governance, and increasing social vices among young people. A nation with a largely unempowered youth population is at risk of facing socio-economic and political instability. Functional and relevant education that aligns with societal needs must, therefore, aim to equip youth with the capabilities necessary for self-determination, self-reliance, financial independence, and meaningful contribution to economic development. Consequently, youth empowerment through education provides young people with the democratic capacity and agency to actively engage in societal and national development processes.

The primary objective of any governmental intervention in youth empowerment is to actively involve young people in the socio-economic and political development of the nation. The term empowerment has been defined by various scholars and institutions in ways that reflect their focus and contextual application. According to the World Bank (2011), empowerment is "the process of enhancing the capacity of individuals or groups to make choices and to transform those choices into desired actions and outcomes." Empowerment, in essence, symbolizes efforts to support or enable individuals to lead meaningful and productive lives. Youth empowerment refers to a developmental strategy aimed at creating opportunities that enable young people to become morally responsible, self-reliant, and economically productive citizens. Vavrus and Fletcher (2006) define youth empowerment as "an attitudinal, structural, and cultural process through which young people gain the ability and authority to make decisions and implement change in their own lives and the lives of others." These perspectives highlight empowerment as a human capacity-building approach designed to foster self-reliance and active participation. In the scholarly work of Olabiyi (2013), youth empowerment is conceptualized as a process of encouraging young people to become active and responsible citizens within their communities, society, and the nation at large. Youth mentoring, as a component of empowerment, provides young people with positive

role models, support, and motivation. It is regarded as one of the most effective means of helping them realize their full potential as productive members of society.

Youth empowerment is a comprehensive process that involves building an individual's capacity in key areas such as skills acquisition, economic and financial literacy, social integration, moral development, and psychological growth. The ultimate goal is to make individuals self-reliant and capable of contributing meaningfully to societal development. Education is universally recognized as the most effective vehicle for promoting and improving the status of youth. It equips them with the knowledge, values, and competencies required for active participation in society and the economy. As Ugwoegbulem (n.d.) rightly noted, there is an urgent need to reposition the educational system in order to adequately equip young people with relevant empowerment skills that can add value to both themselves and their communities. Education also plays a central role in upholding the rights of youth, being aligned with major international conventions focused on youth development and empowerment. Therefore, the provision of functional and qualitative education remains the most effective empowerment strategy any government can offer its citizens

The objectives of Youth empowerment through education are numerous. According to Botswana Core Welfare Indicators Survey (2009 and 2010), youth empowerment initiatives aim to:

- i. Develop good work ethics
- ii. Attain entrepreneurship experiences
- iii. Achieve employment readiness
- iv. Develop skills and competencies that enable them to make positive contributions to the development of their communities
- v. Foster the development of behavioural change
- vi. Instill a sense of responsibility and accountability in them, drawing on their creativity and energy to improve the delivery of public services, reduce youth unemployment, and eradicate poverty among young people (Ministry of Sports and Youths and Culture, 2009)

Skills-based training through education offers numerous benefits and serves as a foundation for achieving the above objectives.

Skill development of the youth empowerment provides.

- i. Skills to diversify the youths for self-actualization, rather than reliance on government alone.
- ii. Equipping the youths to value their handwork.
- iii. Training in basic literary, numeracy and life skills which should be an integral part of the whole system.
- iv. The promotion of the growth and profitability of the youths for self-employment to Enhance the economy.

Challenges Confronting TVET for Job Creation and Wealth Creation

Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) programs are designed to equip individuals with diverse knowledge and practical skills relevant to various occupational fields. However, the effectiveness of these programs depends heavily on the availability of proper infrastructure, adequate training materials, and competent instructors to implement the TVET curriculum. Without these essential inputs, and unless the training process is well-organized and effectively managed, achieving the desired objectives and producing competent graduates becomes a formidable challenge (Awraris, 2013). High-quality skills training require qualified instructors, appropriate workshop equipment, sufficient training materials, and ample opportunities for hands-on practice by learners. According to Igberadja (2014), the implementation of the TVET curriculum in Nigeria has not yielded the expected outcomes. This shortfall is reflected in the persistent complaints from the labor market that Nigerian graduates including those from TVET programs lack employable skills. This deficiency is attributed largely to the poor implementation of the TVET curriculum in educational institutions.

Moreover, TVET delivery systems in many developing countries, including Nigeria, operate under challenging socio-economic conditions and contextual frameworks that need urgent reform for TVET to fulfill its potential as a driver of national development (NICHE, 2010). In many cases, TVET programs are limited in scale, scope, quality, and perceived importance. The curricula are often outdated, and institutions lack the necessary tools and equipment for effective practical training (NICHE, 2010). Puyate, cited in Umar and Ma'aji (2010), highlights the poor state of facilities in Nigerian TVET institutions. There is a notable absence of planned maintenance for broken equipment or strategies for acquiring new tools. Additionally, there appears to be little concern among government officials, teachers, and students regarding the improvement of these facilities.

Similarly, Afeti (2007), as referenced in Audu, Aede, Yusri, and Muhammad (2013), pointed out that the quality of training in Nigerian TVET institutions is generally low, with excessive emphasis on theoretical knowledge and certification rather than on practical skills acquisition and proficiency testing. Factors such as inadequate instructor training, obsolete equipment, and insufficient instructional materials combine to reduce the effectiveness of TVET programs in delivering the required knowledge and skill competencies. Due to these resource constraints, education and training in many TVET institutions remain largely theoretical, resulting in graduates who are often regarded by employers as no more skilled than their academically trained counterparts (Audu et al., 2013). Supporting this view, Uzoagulu (1993), also cited by Audu et al. (2013), asserted that when equipment and tools are non-functional or inadequately provided, technical training programs suffer significantly, and leading to the production of unskilled, unemployable, and unproductive personnel.

According to Ayomike, Okwelle, and Okeke (2013), the challenges hindering the attainment of TVET goals in Nigerian vocational institutions include poor supervision of vocational technical education programs, inadequate provision of instructional materials, obsolete or non-existent facilities, and insufficient funding. Other critical issues involve inadequate

curriculum content for TVET programs, poor welfare packages for vocational technical educators, lack of continuous training and retraining for technical education teachers and instructors, lack of incentives and motivation for teachers, and politicization in the employment process, particularly regarding the appointment of heads of vocational institutions. Similarly, Dasmani (2012), cited in Audu, Aede, Yusri, and Muhammad (2013), reported that inadequate instructional materials, large class sizes, insufficient training facilities, and weak collaboration with local industries for hands-on experience both for trainers and trainees contribute significantly to ineffective and inefficient student training. Furthermore, an undue emphasis on passing examinations over skills acquisition further exacerbates the problem.

The National Board for Technical Education (NBTE, 2011), as reported in Igberadja (2015), identified additional challenges in the TVET sector, including low societal recognition that translates to low enrollment and an inadequate skilled workforce. Other issues cited include obsolete instructional facilities, inadequate funding, poor staffing, weak linkages with industry, and overall deficiencies in quality. Moreover, evaluations in all sectors of education often fail to align with workplace demands, posing further challenges for TVET graduates in the labor market (Audu et al., 2013). The cumulative effect of these challenges is a severe impediment to the effective training of students, resulting in graduates who lack the necessary skills to secure and sustain employment in their respective labor markets (Ogbunaya&Ekereobong, 2015). Audu, Aede, Yusri, and Muhammad (2013) stress that this deplorable condition must be urgently addressed to fulfill the goals of TVET as outlined by the Federal Government of Nigeria in its National Policy on Education. Consequently, the government and all relevant stakeholders must collaborate effectively to ensure that TVET becomes a robust vehicle for job creation and wealth generation.

The Prospects of TVET in Youth Empowerment and Wealth Creation in Nigeria

Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) plays a vital role in addressing unemployment, poverty, and skill gaps among Nigerian youth. The development and expansion of TVET present significant opportunities for empowering young people and fostering sustainable wealth creation. Key areas through which TVET contributes include:

- i. Youth Empowerment through Skill Acquisition: Equipping young individuals with practical and industry-relevant skills to enhance employability and self-reliance.
- ii. Wealth Creation through Entrepreneurship: Encouraging entrepreneurial mindsets and providing the tools needed to start and manage small- and medium-scale enterprises.
- iii. Enhancing Economic Diversification: Reducing over-dependence on limited economic sectors by developing skilled manpower for diverse industries.
- iv. Bridging the Skill Gap: Addressing the mismatch between the skills taught in formal education and those required by the labour market.

Conclusion

Youth empowerment focuses on equipping young people with the necessary skills for self-employment and national development. However, many Nigerian youths lack the functional and relevant education required to become self-reliant due to gaps in the current educational system. Skill acquisition is crucial for boosting productivity and ensuring global competitiveness in today's economy. TVET serves as a strategic educational investment for sustainable youth empowerment and national progress. For Nigeria to thrive as a viable nation, it must harness the energy, creativity, and resourcefulness of its youth population to drive economic growth and innovation. The nation's development is fundamentally linked to the social and economic contributions of its citizens, particularly through vocational and technical training aimed at promoting community and national development. VET, as a branch of education, promotes the acquisition of practical skills and basic scientific knowledge, fostering creativity and innovation among the youth. Empowering young people through TVET can effectively tackle youth unemployment and reduce the prevalence of associated social vices. Ultimately, TVET plays a pivotal role in enhancing the well-being of individuals and communities by increasing productivity, fostering self-reliance, and stimulating entrepreneurship.

Recommendations

- i. Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) should be made compulsory for all youths in Nigeria after secondary school. This will ensure they are equipped with functional skills for self-reliance.
- ii. The government should, as a matter of urgency, raise its current budgetary allocation to education to meet international standards, thereby making the development of TVET and other educational initiatives possible.
- iii. To ensure proper youth empowerment and global relevance, TVET departments should be equipped with mini-industries capable of producing quality consumer goods and services.
- iv. Regular in-service training in developed countries should be sponsored for all TVET educators at all levels. This will expose them to modern industrial practices and innovations.
- v. The government and TVET stakeholders should collaborate to revitalize TVET at all levels of education.
- vi. The TVET curriculum should be reviewed and aligned with the current needs of the nation to make it more effective and responsive.
- vii. The TVET system should be fully adopted as a strategic youth empowerment tool to tackle the issue of youth unemployment.
- viii. Nigerian youths should be consistently supported with access to credit facilities to enable them to establish small-scale businesses, reducing their dependence on white-collar jobs.

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